

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

SYNTHESIS, ANTITUBERCULAR AND ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITIES OF NOVEL PYRROLYL BENZOHYDRAZIDE DERIVATIVES

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 21/08/2018

Available online

31/08/2018

Keywords

Pyrrole,
Antitubercular Agents,
HBTU,
DIEA,
Benzohydrazides.

ABSTRACT

Novel series of pyrrole derivatives were synthesized with an approach to reduce the growing anti-tubercular resistance and to develop more potent and less side effect anti-tubercular agents. Herein, we synthesized a series of substituted 2-phenoxybenzamide derivatives (3a-j) by reacting different phenoxy acetic acids with 4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzoate (2) and a series of pyrrolyl benzamides (6a-c) were synthesized by reacting 4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzoic acid with different hydrazides 2, (5a-b) using HBTU as a coupling agent, DIEA as a catalyst and DMF as a solvent. Structures of all the newly synthesized compounds were confirmed by spectral analysis viz., IR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and Mass. Further they were tested for their anti-tubercular and antibacterial activities and compounds showed moderate to good activity.

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Please cite this article in press as **Dr. Shrinivas D. Joshi et al.** Synthesis, Antitubercular and Antibacterial Activities of Novel Pyrrolyl Benzohydrazide Derivatives. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2018;8(08).

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INTRODUCTION

Tuberculosis (TB) is an antique, contagious disease caused by five closely related mycobacteria such as *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, *Mycobacterium bovis*, *Mycobacterium africanum*, *Mycobacterium microti* and *Mycobacterium canetti*. Among these, *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (*M. tuberculosis*) by far the most causative agent for TB [1, 2] and is characterized by tubercle lesions in the lungs [3]. It has infected man since the birth of civilization and despite the introduction of TB chemotherapy in the 1950s it has made a dramatic resurgence in the past decades and it still remains a leading infectious disease worldwide [4]. TB is the second-leading cause in mortalities and is responsible for infecting one-third of the world's population. The World Health Organization (WHO) estimated 1.4 million deaths in 2011 are due to TB, which included 350,000 TB, associated HIV infected deaths [5-7] and also significant lack of patient adherence to long-term therapy leads to the emergence of multidrug-resistant (MDR-TB) and extensive drug resistance (XDR-TB) that has become a major threat to human kind [8].

Pyrrole and its derivatives have shown to possess biological activities such as antibacterial, antitumor, analgesics, antitubercular, anti-inflammatory, and anti-allergic [9-14]. Several macromolecular antibiotics having pyrrole structure were isolated from biological sources and their activities were defined [15, 16] It is an important heterocycle in plant and animal kingdom because of its participation as a subunit of chlorophyll in plant cells and hemin and vitamin B₁₂ in animal cells, Pyrrole and its derivatives have shown significant antimycobacterial activities. Keeping in view of the biological and medicinal properties of pyrroles and the potentiality of peptide linkage, we have undertaken to synthesize such molecules that contain both pyrrole and peptide linkages to treat against the resistant bacterial species.

In this work, we have synthesized some pyrrolyl benzohydrazide derivatives by reacting different phenoxy acetic acids with pyrrolyl benzohydrazide and also by reacting different hydrazides with pyrrolyl benzoic acid using HBTU as a coupling agent and DIEA as a catalyst and DMF as a solvent to get the titled product.

Experimental

All the chemicals used in the synthetic experiment were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich, S. D. Fine-Chem Limited and Spectrochem Pvt. Ltd. Solvents used were of reagent grade and they were purified and dried by the standard methods. Melting points were determined using the Shital-digital programmable melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. FTIR spectra in KBr pellets were recorded on a Bruker FTIR spectrophotometer. The ¹H spectra were recorded on a Bruker AVANCE II at 400 MHz, chemical shifts are expressed in parts per million (*ppm*) relative to TMS. The abbreviations used to describe the peak patterns are: (*s*) singlet, (*d*) doublet, (*t*) triplet and (*m*) multiplet. Mass spectra (MS) were recorded in a JEOL GCMATE II GC-Mass spectrometer and Shimadzu QP 20105 GC-Mass spectrometer. Analytical thin-layer chromatography (TLC) was performed on precoated TLC sheets of silica gel 60 F254 (Merck, Darmstadt, Germany) visualized by long- and short- wavelength ultraviolet (UV) lamps.

SCHEME I:

SCHEME II:

General procedure for the synthesis of aryloxy acetic acids (1a-j):

Equimolar quantities of 2-chloro acetic acid (0.05 mol) and substituted phenols (0.05 mol) were taken in a conical flask, to which aqueous solution of NaOH (0.12 mol in 25 mL water) was slowly added with constant stirring. The solution was stirred for 2 h until the solution turned clear, brown or yellow and then the reaction mixture was evaporated in an evaporating dish until the solid sodium salt was precipitated. The salt was isolated, dried, dissolved in water and acidified by adding con. HCl. The precipitated aryloxy acetic acid was filtered and recrystallized from water or ethanol [17].

Synthesis of 4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazide (2):

Compound **2** was synthesized by refluxing a mixture of ethyl 4-pyrrol-1-yl benzoate (3.22 g, 0.015 mol) with hydrazine hydrate (10 mL) in absolute ethanol (10 mL) for 3 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and crystalline mass obtained was recrystallized from ethanol and obtained as yellow crystals [18].

General procedure for the synthesis of N'-2-(substituted phenoxyacetyl)-4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzo hydrazides (3a-j):

Stirred mixture of 0.0018 mol of 4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazide (**2**), 0.0091 mol of aryloxyacetic acids (**1a-j**) in DMF, HBTU (0.0023mol, 0.87g) and DIEA (0.0053mol, 0.93ml) at room temperature for 25 h and the reaction was monitored by TLC after the completion of reaction, the mixture was quenched by brine and then it is extracted with ethylacetate (3 x 50ml), then the ethylacetate layer was washed with 1N HCl and saturated NaHCO₃ solution followed by brine, then the organic layer was evaporated using rotary flash evaporator to obtain compounds **3(a-j)** and further compounds were purified by column chromatography using chloroform: methanol (9:1) as mobile phase and iodine vapours as visualizing agents.

N'-(2-Phenoxyacetyl)-4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazide (3a)

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹: 3368, 3127 (-NH), 2853, 2923 (CH-Ar), 1637, 1610 (C=O); ¹H NMR (400MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 3.16-3.18 (2H, s, -OCH₂), 6.37-6.38 (2H, t, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.13-7.15 (3H, t, phenoxy-C₂, C₄, C₆-H), 7.26-7.61 (6H, m, pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H; phenoxy-C₃, C₅-H and bridging phenyl-C₂, C₆-H), 7.88-7.97 (2H, d, bridging phenyl-C₃, C₅-H), 9.89 (2H, s, -NH); MS (EI) m/z: 338.62 (M+3).

4-(1H-Pyrrol-1-yl)-N'-(2-(o-tolyloxy)acetyl)benzohydrazide (3b)

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹: 3232 (-NH), 3349 (-NH), 2852, 2921 (CH- Ar), 1641, 1610 (C=O); ¹H NMR (400MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 3.16-3.18 (5H, s, -OCH₂ and -CH₃), 6.35-6.41 (2H, m, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.09-7.57 (6H, m, pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H and phenoxy-C₃, C₄, C₅, C₆-H), 7.94-8.00 (4H, m, bridging phenyl-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H), 10.12 (2H, s, -NH). ¹³C NMR (100MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 12.90, 54.62, 111.37, 111.90, 119.20, 119.50, 127.56, 129.16, 129.77, 143.36, 154.48, 162.42, 165.83.

4-(1H-Pyrrol-1-yl)-N-(2-(p-tolyloxy)acetyl)benzohydrazide (3c):

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹: 3127, 3111 (-NH,-NH), 2851, 2922 (CH- Ar), 1639, 1690 (C=O). ¹H NMR (400MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 3.16 (5H, s, -CH₃ and -OCH₂), 6.37-6.38 (2H, t, pyrrole-C₃,C₄-H), 7.13-7.14 (4H, t, phenoxy-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H), 7.26 (2H, s, pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H), 7.45-7.47 (2H, dd, bridgingphenyl-C₂, C₆-H), 7.95-7.97 (2H, dd, bridgingphenyl-C₃, C₅-H), 9.89 (2H, s, -NH). ¹³C NMR (100MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 21.08, 54.13, 111.64, 113.92, 119.93, 121.22, 129.60, 141.60, 152.28, 166.57.

N'-(2-(4-Fluorophenoxy)acetyl)-4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazide (3d)

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹: 3127, 3214 (-NH,-NH), 2851, 2921 (CH-Ar), 1638, 1611 (C=O); ¹H NMR (400MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 3.1-3.18 (2H, s, -OCH₂), 6.37-6.38 (2H, t, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.13-7.14 (4H, t, phenoxy-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H), 7.26 (2H, s, pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H), 7.45-7.47 (2H, dd, bridgingphenyl-C₂, C₆-H), 7.94-7.97 (2H, dd, bridging phenyl-C₃, C₅-H), 9.88 (2H, s, -NH). ¹³C NMR (100MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 54.12, 111.66, 118.93, 119.37, 119.93, 127.21, 129.77, 143.33, 153.33, 162.41, 165.93.

N'-(2-(4-Nitrophenoxy)acetyl)-4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazide (3e)

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹: 3238, 3382 (-NH,-NH), 2851,2919 (CH-Ar), 1639,1610 (C=O); ¹H NMR (400MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 3.10-3.18 (m, 2H, -OCH₂), 7.01-7.19 (m, 4H, pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H and phenoxy-C₂, C₆-H), 7.36-7.59 (m, 2H, bridging phenyl-C₂, C₆-H), 7.87-7.98 (m, 3H; phenoxy-C₃ and bridgingphenyl-C₃, C₅-H), 9.84 (s, 2H, -NH), 6.35-6.41 (m, 4H, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H and -NH₂). ¹³C NMR (100MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 59.08, 111.64, 111.89, 119.20, 119.39, 119.92, 127.54, 129.76, 143.33, 162.41, 165.83.

N'-(2-(2-Chlorophenoxy)acetyl)-4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazide (3f)

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹: 3225 (-NH), 3139 (-NH), 2922, 2956 (CH-Ar), 1690 (C=O). ¹H NMR (400MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 2.54 (2H, s, -OCH₂), 6.30 (2H, s, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.26 (1H, s, phenyl-C₆), 7.31 (1H, s, phenyl-C₄), 7.38 (2H, s, pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H), 7.49-8.07 (6H, m, phenoxy-C₃, C₅-H and bridging phenyl-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H), 10.31 (1H, s, NH), 9.90 (1H, s, NH). ¹³C NMR (100MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 54.22, 111.89, 136.57, 131.57, 143.33, 162.42, 165.83.

N'-(2-(3-Chlorophenoxy)acetyl)-4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazide (3g)

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹: 3346 (-NH), 3236 (-NH), 2923 (CH-Ar), 1643 (C=O); ¹H NMR (400MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 2.94 (2H, s, -OCH₂), 6.32 (2H, s, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.32-7.68 (8H, m, pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H, bridgingphenyl-C₂, C₆-H and phenoxy-C₂, C₄, C₅, C₆-H), 7.63-7.68 (4H, t, pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H and 3-Clph-C₂, C₅-H), 7.37 (2H, s, 3-Clph-C₄, C₆-H), 8.00-8.12 (4H, m, bridgingphenyl-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H), 11.05 (2H, s, -NH).

N'-(2-(2-Bromophenoxy)acetyl)-4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazide (3h)

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm⁻¹: 3364 (-NH), 3216 (-NH), 2851-2922 (CH-Ar), 1642 (C=O); ¹H NMR (400MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 3.16-3.18 (2H, s, -OCH₂), 6.36-6.38 (2H, s, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.10-7.52 (6H, m, pyrrole-C₂, C₅ and phenoxy-C₃, C₄, C₅, C₆-H), 7.87-7.98 (4H, m, bridgingphenyl-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H), 9.85 (2H, s, -NH). ¹³C NMR (100MHz, δ ppm, CDCl₃): 111.65, 111.90, 111.21, 111.39, 111.50, 111.94, 127.20, 129.77, 135.35, 145.76, 155.86, 165.86.

***N'*-(2-(3-Bromophenoxy)acetyl)-4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazide (3i)**

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 3362 (-NH), 3219 (-NH), 2851-2920 (CH-Ar), 1640 (C=O); ^1H NMR (400MHz, δ ppm, CDCl_3): 3.13 (2H, s, -OCH₂), 6.35-6.38 (2H, m, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 6.72-7.68 (6H, m, pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H and phenoxy-C₂, C₄, C₅, C₆-H), 7.87-7.90 (4H, m, bridgingphenyl-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H), 10.23 (2H, s, -NH). ^{13}C NMR (100MHz, δ ppm, CDCl_3): 54.30, 111.90, 119.21, 119.49, 143.31, 154.31, 162.41, 165.84

***N'*-(2-(4-Iodophenoxy)acetyl)-4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazide (3j)**

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 3347 (-NH), 3233 (-NH), 2852-2923 (CH-Ar), 1645 (C=O); ^1H NMR (400MHz, δ ppm, CDCl_3): 3.17 (2H, s, -OCH₂), 6.32 (2H, s, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.31-7.41 (4H, m, phenoxy-C₂, C₆-H and pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H), 7.59 (2H, d, phenoxy-C₃, C₅-H), 7.84 (2H, d, bridging phenyl-C₂, C₆-H), 8.03 (2H, d, bridgingphenyl-C₃, C₅-H).

Procedure for the synthesis of 4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzoic acid (4)

To a solution of 4-aminobenzoic acid (10 mmol) in 20 ml glacial acetic acid was added slowly 2,5-dimethoxytetrahydrofuran (15 mmol) at room temperature and the mixture was refluxed for 45 min. The reaction mixture was poured onto crushed ice and neutralized by adding saturated solution of NaHCO₃. The separated solid was collected, washed with water, dried and recrystallized from ethanol. [18]

General procedure for the synthesis of *N'*-(formyl)-4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazides (6a-c):

A mixture of 0.0018 mol of 4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzoic acid, 0.0019 mol of different hydrazides [2, 5(a-b)] were dissolved in dry DMF (20ml), HBTU (0.0023 mol) and DIEA (0.93ml) were added and stirred for 25 h at room temperature and the reaction was monitored by TLC after the completion of reaction, the mixture was quenched by brine and then it is extracted with ethylacetate (3 x 50 ml), then the ethylacetate layer was washed with 1N HCl and saturated NaHCO₃ solution followed by brine, then the organic layer was evaporated using rotary flash evaporator to obtain compounds 6(a-c) and further compounds were purified by column chromatography using chloroform: pet. ether (9:1) as mobile phase and iodine vapours as visualizing agents.

***N'*-(4-1H-Pyrrol-1-yl)benzoyl-4-(1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazide (6a):**

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 3415 (-NH), 2921, 2851 (CH-Ar), 1608 (C=O). ^1H NMR (400MHz, δ ppm, CDCl_3): 6.28-6.32 (4H, m, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H and pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.35-7.39 (4H, m, pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H and pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H), 7.60-8.10 (8H, m, ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H and ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H), 9.99 (2H, s, -2NH), ^{13}C NMR (100MHz, δ ppm CDCl_3): 111.83, 119.04, 119.41, 128.41, 130.74, 143.83, 161.74.

***N'*-(4-1H-Pyrrol-1-yl)-4-(2,5-dimethyl-1H-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazide (6b)**

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 3216 (-NH), 3005, 2920 (CH-Ar), 1635 (C=O); ^1H NMR (400MHz, δ ppm CDCl_3): 2.00 (6H, s, -2CH₃), 5.90 (2H, s, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 6.37 (2H, t, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.09 (2H, t, pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H), 7.25 (2H, d, bridging phenyl-C₂, C₆-H), 7.36 (2H, d, bridging phenyl-C₃, C₅-H), 8.01 (4H, m, ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H), 10.25 (2H, s, -2NH). ^{13}C NMR (100MHz, δ ppm CDCl_3): 13.27, 107.0, 111.80, 119.41, 142.85, 166.69.

***N'*-(4-1H-Pyrrol-1-yl)benzoyl)isonicotinohydrazide (6c)**

IR (KBr) ν_{\max} , cm^{-1} : 3416 (-NH), 2920, 2851 (CH-Ar), 1614 (C=O); ^1H NMR (400 MHz, δ ppm CDCl_3): 6.29-6.32 (m, 2H, pyrrole-C₃, C₄-H), 7.01- 8.17 (m, 8H, pyrrole-C₂, C₅-H; bridging ph-C₂, C₃, C₅, C₆-H; pyridine-C₃, C₅-H), 8.57-8.58 (2H, m, pyridine-C₂, C₆-H), 9.96 (2H, s, -2NH). ^{13}C NMR (100MHz, δ ppm CDCl_3): 111.80, 119.02, 119.48, 123.47, 131.49, 143.42, 150.33, 167.33. MS (EI): m/z = Found =308.37 [M+2]; Calcd. = 306.

Biological activity:**Antitubercular activity**

MIC values were determined for pyrrolyl phenoxy and benzamide derivatives against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv strain by Microplate Alamar Blue assay (MABA) [19] using INH as the standard drug. The 96 wells plate received 100 μL of Middlebrook 7H9 broth and serial dilution of compounds were made directly on the plate with drug concentrations of 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.6, 3.125, 6.25, 12.5, 25, 50 and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. Plates were covered, sealed with parafilm and incubated at 37 C for 5 days. Then, 25 μL of freshly prepared 1:1 mixture of almar blue reagent and 10% Tween 80 were added to the plate and incubated for 24 h. A blue color in the well was interpreted as no bacterial growth and pink color was scored as the growth. The MIC was defined as the lowest drug concentration, which prevented the color change from blue to pink. Table 2 reveals antitubercular activity (MIC) data.

Antibacterial activity

MIC determination of the tested compounds was investigated by a side-by-side comparison with norfloxacin and ciprofloxacin against Gram-positive (*S. aureus*) and Gram-negative bacteria (*E. coli*) by the broth microdilution method [20, 21]. Serial dilutions of the test compounds and reference drugs were prepared in Mueller-Hinton agar. Drugs (10 mg) were dissolved in dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO, 1 mL). Further progressive dilutions with the molten Mueller-Hinton agar were performed to obtain the required concentrations of 0.2, 0.4, 0.8, 1.6, 3.125, 6.25, 12.5, 25, 50 and 100 mg/mL. The tubes were inoculated with 10⁵ cfu mL⁻¹ (colony forming unit/mL) and incubated at 37 °C for 18 h. MIC was the lowest concentration of the tested compound that yielded no visible growth on the plate. To ensure that solvent had no effect on bacterial growth, a control was performed with the test medium supplemented with DMSO at the same dilutions as used in the experiments and DMSO had no effect on the microorganisms in the concentrations studied. Table 3 reveals the antibacterial activity (MIC values) data

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Synthesis

Synthetic route adopted to obtain the target compounds are depicted in Scheme I & II. FTIR, ¹H NMR, ¹³C NMR and mass spectral data are in agreement with the proposed structures of all the synthesized compounds. The physicochemical properties of the newly synthesized compounds are depicted in Table 1.

Table 1. Physical data of the synthesized compounds:

Comp.	R	Yield (%)	Mobile phase for Chromatography	Column	M.P (°C)	Molecular Formula
3a	-H	75	Chloroform: Methanol		126-128	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃
3b	2-CH ₃	60	Chloroform: Methanol		130-132	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₃
3c	4-CH ₃	65	Chloroform: Methanol		132-134	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₃ O ₃
3d	4-F	60	Chloroform: Methanol		144-146	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ F
3e	4-NO ₂	70	Chloroform: Methanol		172-174	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₅ N
3f	2-Cl	75	Chloroform: Methanol		138-140	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ Cl
3g	3-Cl	60	Chloroform: Methanol		148-150	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ Cl
3h	2-Br	65	Chloroform: Methanol		140-142	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ Br
3i	3-Br	60	Chloroform: Methanol		136-138	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ Br
3j	4-I	70	Chloroform: Methanol		168-170	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ I
6a		60	Chloroform: Petroleum ether		184-190	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₃
6b		62	Chloroform: Petroleum ether		122-126	C ₂₅ H ₂₄ N ₆ O ₃
6c		65	Chloroform: Petroleum ether		206-210	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₃

All the synthesized compounds of pyrrolyl benzohydrazide derivatives (**3a-j** & **6a-c**) were obtained in a good yield and their structures were established by NMR spectral analysis, FTIR spectra of compound 3c showed the presence of C=O peak at 1639 & 1690 cm⁻¹ and -NH's peak at 3127 & 3111 cm⁻¹, further the structure of compound 3c was confirmed by ¹H NMR spectra which showed the presence of two -NH as singlet at 9.89 ppm, and a peak at 3.16 ppm was attributed to the presence of -CH₃ & -OCH₂. ¹³C NMR spectra showed a peak at 165.93, 162.41, 54.12 ppm which was attributed to the presence of carbonyl group, -CH₃ and -OCH₂.

Biological activity

Antitubercular Activity

All the synthesized compounds (**3a-j** and **6a-c**) were screened against *M. tuberculosis* H37Rv strain which showed MIC value ranging from 3.12-25 µg/ml. Among all the screened compounds, compounds **3a**, **3d**, **3(f-i)** and **6c** inhibited microorganism growth efficiently compared to other synthesized compounds in the series with a MIC value of 3.12 µg/ml, and the compounds **3a**, **3c** and **6a** showed a moderate activity with MIC value of 25 and 12.5 µg/ml respectively (Table 2).

Antibacterial Activity

The results of antimicrobial activities (expressed in MIC) of the compounds against selected Gram-positive and Gram-negative bacteria are illustrated in Tables 2. The activity of ciprofloxacin and norfloxacin are used for comparison. All the compounds showed moderate to significant microbial inhibition. Pyrrolyl derivatives have shown antibacterial activity between MIC of 3.12-100 µg/ml. Compounds **3a**, **3d**, **3f** and **3i** have showed highest activity against *E. coli* at MIC value of 3.12 µg/ml than the other tested compounds. (Table 2).

Table 2: *In vitro* antitubercular and antibacterial activity results of newly synthesized compounds.

Comp.	<i>In vitro</i> antitubercular activity MIC value ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	<i>In vitro</i> antitubercular activity MIC value ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	
		Gram +ve (<i>S. aureus</i>)	Gram -ve (<i>E. coli</i>)
3a	3.12	50	3.12
3b	25	>100	12.5
3c	12.5	100	12.5
3d	3.12	>100	3.12
3e	6.25	25	12.5
3f	3.12	50	3.12
3g	3.12	-	-
3h	3.12	100	6.25
3i	3.12	>100	3.12
3j	6.25	100	12.5
6a	12.5	100	6.25
6b	6.25	>100	12.5
6c	3.12	100	6.25
Pyrazinamide	3.125	--	--
Streptomycin	6.25	--	--
Ciprofloxacin	--	2	2
Norfloxacin	--	3	12

CONCLUSION

Novel series of *N'*-2-(substituted phenoxyacetyl)-4-(1*H*-pyrrol-1-yl)benzo hydrazides (**3a-j**) and *N'*-(formyl)-4-(1*H*-pyrrol-1-yl)benzohydrazides (**6(a-c)**) were synthesized and identified as potent antitubercular and antibacterial agents. Among all the compounds **3a**, **3d**, **3(f-i)** and **6c** have displayed significant activity against *M. tuberculosis* with MIC value of 3.125 µg/ml. These compounds will be useful as the lead compounds for developing antitubercular and antibacterial agents.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS:

°C	Degree centigrade
CDCl ₃	Deuterated chloroform
FTIR	Fourier Transfer Infrared Spectroscopy
NMR	Nuclear Magnetic Resonance
ppm	Parts per million
MP	Melting point
R _f	Retention factor
Min	Minutes
H	Hours
Mol	Mole
TLC	Thin Layer Chromatography
MIC	Minimum Inhibitory Concentration
HBTU	2-(1 <i>H</i> -Benzotriazole-1-yl)-1,1,3,3-tetramethyluroniumhexafluorophosphate
DIEA	NN-Diisopropylethylamine
DMF	NN-Dimethylformamide

Conflict of Interests

All the authors have no conflict of interests.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

Authors immensely thank research support from the Indian Council of Medical Research, New Delhi [ICMR letter Ref No. BIC/12(13)2014 dated 13-02-2017 (IRIS Cell No. 2014-2676)]. We also thank Dr. V. H. Kulkarni, Principal, Dr. T. M. Aminabhavi, Research Director and Dr. H. V. Dambal, President, S.E.T's College of Pharmacy, Dharwad, Karnataka, India for providing the facilities. We thank Dr. K.G. Bhat of Maratha Mandal's Dental College, Hospital and Research Centre, Belgaum, Karnataka, India, for providing antibacterial and antitubercular activities. SAIF, Panjab University, Chandigarh, Panjab, India provided some of the NMR and mass spectral data.

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